

Abnormal Activity Detection in scene using Unsupervised Machine Learning

Dr. Yashaswini S¹, Meghdeep Mondal², Mohammed Abyan K³, Ayushman Muduli⁴

¹Associate professor, Dept. of CSE, Cambridge Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

²UG Scholar, Dept. of CSE, Cambridge Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

³UG Scholar, Dept. of CSE, Cambridge Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

⁴UG Scholar, Dept. of CSE, Cambridge Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Abstract—Abnormal activity detection in surveillance videos is one of the most crucial task in computer vision with applications in security and intelligent monitoring. This paper presents an unsupervised deep learning approach utilizing a convolutional autoencoder combined with temporal modeling via ConvLSTM to detect anomalies in real-world scenes. The model is trained on the ShanghaiTech dataset using normal activity sequences and identifies anomalies based on reconstruction errors. To enhance performance, we incorporate Optical Flow for motion-aware feature extraction and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) loss for improved perceptual reconstruction quality. The model is evaluated using precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC which were found to be 0.570, 0.065, 0.105, 0.626 respectively, achieving improved anomaly detection accuracy. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in detecting complex anomalies while reducing false positives. This approach contributes to real-time, scalable, and generalizable anomaly detection systems in video surveillance.

Keywords— Abnormal Activity Detection, Unsupervised Learning, Autoencoders, Surveillance, Deep Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid progress in artificial intelligence and computer vision has transformed video surveillance, driving its extensive adoption in public spaces, transportation hubs, industries, and critical infrastructure.

With the proliferation of CCTV and smart surveillance systems[1], the sheer volume of video data generated has exceeded the capacity of manual monitoring, necessitating the development of automated abnormal activity detection (AAD) systems[2]. These systems are crucial for identifying threats, ensuring public safety, and responding to emergencies in real-time. Traditional surveillance monitoring relies on human operators, which is inefficient due to fatigue, inconsistent attention span, and the impracticality of monitoring multiple video feeds simultaneously. This has driven research into intelligent anomaly detection systems capable of automatically identifying unusual activities in real-world environments[3].

Most conventional approaches to abnormal activity detection are supervised deep learning models, where labelled datasets of normal and abnormal activities are used to train a classifier. However, real-world anomaly detection presents several key challenges that make supervised methods impractical. The first challenge is the lack of labelled anomaly data. Anomalies are inherently unpredictable and rare, making it difficult to create large-scale labelled datasets that adequately represent all possible types of abnormal

activities. Manually annotating anomalies is expensive and time-consuming. The second challenge is the diversity and context-dependence of anomalies. Anomalous behaviours vary significantly across different environments. For example, running in a pedestrian area may be considered anomalous, whereas the same action in a park is normal. A model trained in a scenario may not necessarily generalize well to other scenarios.

Another major challenge is the imbalance in class distribution. Normal activities vastly outnumber abnormal events in surveillance footage, leading to class imbalance in supervised learning. Additionally, the need for real-time detection imposes strict computational efficiency requirements, as high-latency systems are impractical for real-world security applications. Finally, the dynamic and unpredictable nature of anomalies makes it difficult to define a fixed set of anomalous patterns, unlike structured tasks such as image classification. These challenges highlight the need for an unsupervised learning approach, where the model learns normal activity patterns and detects anomalies based on deviations from these patterns.

To tend to these sorts of challenges, this paper proposes an unsupervised deep learning approach that learns normal behaviour patterns from video sequences and detects anomalies based on deviations from the learned patterns. The proposed approach leverages a Convolutional Autoencoder (CAE) combined with Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (ConvLSTM) [4] to model both spatial and temporal dependencies in video sequences. Autoencoders (AEs) are widely used for anomaly detection as they learn to encode and reconstruct normal data, while anomalies manifest as high reconstruction errors due to their deviation from normal patterns. ConvLSTMs, on the other hand, capture temporal dynamics, enabling the detection of sudden or unexpected motion patterns.

Despite the advantages of autoencoder-based anomaly detection[5], conventional models suffer from false positives, as they may reconstruct anomalies with reasonable accuracy, leading to low reconstruction error. To address this, we incorporate Optical Flow[6] as an additional motion-sensitive feature extraction mechanism. Optical Flow estimates pixel-wise motion between consecutive frames, allowing the model to differentiate normal movements from abrupt, unusual activity. Furthermore, instead of relying on Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss, we integrate Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) loss to improve anomaly localization and perceptual fidelity. SSIM loss is more sensitive to structural changes, ensuring that fine-grained anomalies such as a person

loitering or sudden movement in a crowd are captured effectively.

The primary contributions of this paper include the development of an unsupervised deep learning framework for abnormal activity detection using a Convolutional Autoencoder (CAE) with ConvLSTM for spatial-temporal feature learning. Additionally, we integrate Optical Flow as an auxiliary motion-aware feature extractor to improve anomaly localization and reduce false positives. We also replace MSE loss with SSIM loss[7] to enhance perceptual reconstruction quality, leading to improved detection of subtle anomalies. Finally, we provide a comprehensive evaluation on the ShanghaiTech dataset, demonstrating improved precision, recall, and F1-score compared to baseline unsupervised methods.

II. CONV LSTM MODEL FOR UNSUPERVISED DETECTION

Autoencoders are a preferable approach for unsupervised anomaly detection as they learn to encode and reconstruct input data. A well trained autoencoder is expected to reconstruct normal frames accurately, while abnormal frames, which deviate from learned patterns, result in higher reconstruction errors. In this model, a Convolutional Autoencoder[8] is used to extract spatial features from individual video frames. The encoder component consists of stacked convolutional layers that progressively extract high level feature representations, reducing the dimensionality of input frames while preserving critical spatial information. The decoder component employs transposed convolutional layers to reconstruct the original input frames. The difference between the input and reconstructed frame serves as an indicator of abnormality.

Fig.1 : A convolutional-LSTM model cell

The Fig.1 illustrates the internal mechanism of ConvLSTM. Each cell consists of gates (input, forget, and output gates) that regulate the flow of information, while the cell state maintains long-term dependencies. The convolutional layers replace fully connected layers, allowing spatial information to be preserved across frames. Batch normalization (BN) improves training stability. The final hidden state encodes the temporal evolution of the input sequence, making ConvLSTM a powerful choice for video-based anomaly detection.

Given an input frame, the encoder applies a series of convolutional layers with rectified linear unit activation to extract hierarchical feature representations. The encoded features are then passed through the Convolutional Long Short Term Memory layers to model sequential dependencies in video frames. Finally, the decoder reconstructs the frames from the learned representations, and the difference between the input and reconstructed frames is used to determine anomaly scores. The reconstruction loss, measured using Structural Similarity Index loss, determines the anomaly score.

While Convolutional Autoencoders capture spatial features[9], they lack an understanding of motion patterns and temporal dependencies between consecutive frames. To address this, a Convolutional Long Short Term Memory network is integrated after the encoder to model spatiotemporal dependencies. Convolutional Long Short Term Memory networks extend traditional Long Short Term Memory networks by incorporating convolutional operations inside the Long Short Term Memory cell, making them well suited for processing sequential video data. For a given sequence of frames, the Convolutional Long Short Term Memory unit stores memory across time steps and updates hidden states based on previous frames. This enables the model to detect motion anomalies, such as sudden movements or abnormal speed variations, by learning patterns from normal motion sequences.

Since most anomalies involve motion changes such as running, fighting, and loitering, the model is further enhanced with Optical Flow, which captures pixel wise motion between consecutive frames. Optical Flow is computed using the Farneback method in Open Computer Vision[10], where it estimates the displacement of pixels from one frame to the next. This motion information helps the model differentiate normal movements from abrupt, unusual activity. The magnitude of motion vectors helps detect motion anomalies more effectively, complementing the spatial features learned by the autoencoder.

Traditional autoencoders use Mean Squared Error to minimize pixel wise reconstruction loss. However, Mean Squared Error treats all pixel differences equally, which fails to capture perceptual distortions that occur in anomalies. Instead, this model uses Structural Similarity Index loss, which is more sensitive to local structural changes in the image. Structural Similarity Index [11] measures the similarity between two images based on luminance, contrast, and structural information, making it more effective in detecting anomalies that involve subtle texture and structure changes rather than just intensity differences. A high Structural Similarity Index loss indicates poor reconstruction, which is more likely in anomalous frames. Using Structural Similarity Index instead of Mean Squared Error ensures that abnormal frame distortions are captured more effectively, improving the model's precision in detecting anomalies.

After training, the model computes reconstruction errors for test sequences. Higher reconstruction errors indicate greater deviation from normal patterns, suggesting an anomaly. The final anomaly score is a weighted combination of Structural Similarity Index based reconstruction error and Optical Flow motion difference. The anomaly score is

computed using tuning parameters that balance spatial and motion based anomaly detection. The final decision is made by applying an adaptive threshold based on Receiver Operating Characteristic analysis, which optimizes the True Positive Rate and False Positive Rate trade-off. Instead of using a fixed threshold for anomaly detection, the model dynamically selects the optimal threshold based on the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve, which helps maximize precision and recall while minimizing false positives.

The proposed unsupervised deep learning framework for abnormal activity detection combines a Convolutional Autoencoder, Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory, Optical Flow, and Structural Similarity Index loss to efficiently identify spatial and motion anomalies in video surveillance. The combination of deep learning for feature extraction, motion-based anomaly tracking, and perceptual loss functions significantly improves precision, recall, and F1 score, as demonstrated in experimental results.

The key advantages of the proposed model include its ability to operate in an unsupervised setting without requiring labelled anomaly data, making it highly scalable for real world deployment. By leveraging ConvLSTM for sequential learning[12], the model learns both appearance based and motion based anomalies without requiring explicit feature engineering. Optical Flow enhances motion awareness [13], reducing false positives, while Structural Similarity Index loss ensures perceptual fidelity, leading to better detection of subtle anomalies. Finally, by optimizing the threshold dynamically using Receiver Operating Characteristic analysis, the model achieves a balanced trade-off between precision and recall, making it suitable for real time anomaly detection in surveillance applications.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Creation

The dataset used in this research is the ShanghaiTech Campus dataset[14], a widely recognized benchmark for anomaly detection in surveillance videos. This dataset consists of 13 different scenes recorded from various surveillance cameras, capturing both normal and abnormal activities. It contains 330 training videos with only normal activities and 107 testing videos, where both normal and abnormal activities are present. The dataset is particularly suitable for unsupervised learning, as the training data does not include any labeled anomalies[15], allowing the model to learn normal patterns without explicit supervision.

Each video in the dataset is recorded at a **resolution of 856 x 480 pixels**, with a frame rate of **25 frames per second**. The videos depict various real-world scenarios, including pedestrians walking on campus, cyclists, people running, fighting, or engaging in unusual behaviours. The anomalies in the test set include actions such as **loitering, sudden running, and physical altercations**, which are significantly different from normal activities[16].

For this study, the dataset was structured into three primary folders for testing:

1. **Frames:** Contains video frames extracted from testing videos, organized into subdirectories by video name.
2. **Test Frame Masks:** Contains binary masks indicating whether a particular frame is normal or anomalous.
3. **Test Pixel Masks:** Provides pixel-wise annotations highlighting the specific regions in a frame where anomalies occur.

The ShanghaiTech dataset is chosen for this research due to its diversity, real-world applicability, and the presence of complex anomalies that closely resemble real surveillance scenarios.

TABLE-1: SHANGHAI DATASET COMPARED TO OTHER RELATED DATASETS

Dataset	#Frames					#Abnormal Events	#Scenes
	Total	Training	Testing	Regularity	Irregularity		
Our Dataset	317,398	274,515	42,883	300,308	17,090	130	13
CUHK Avenue	30,652	15,328	15,324	26,832	3,820	47	1
UCSD Ped2	4,560	2,550	2,010	2,924	1,636	12	1
UCSD Ped1	14,000	6,800	7,200	9,995	4,005	40	1
Subway Entrance	136,524	20,000	116,524	134,124	2,400	66	1
Subway Exit	72,401	7,500	64,901	71,681	720	19	1

Below are Graphical comparisons for the Table-1,

Fig .2 : Frame Distribution in different datasets

Fig.3 : Regular and Irregular Frame distribution in different datasets

Fig.4 : Abnormal events and number of Scenes in different datasets

B. Pre Processing of images

To Pre-processing is a crucial step in preparing the dataset for training and testing. Since the original videos in the dataset are in AVI format, each video is converted into individual frames for efficient processing. The following steps are performed to ensure consistency in the dataset:

1. **Frame Extraction:** Each video is decomposed into individual frames at a fixed interval to ensure uniformity in processing. The frames are stored as grayscale images to reduce computational complexity while preserving structural details.
2. **Resizing:** All frames are resized to **64 x 64 pixels**, ensuring that the model receives standardized input while reducing memory requirements.
3. **Normalization:** The pixel values of frames are normalized to the range **[0,1]** to improve convergence during training. This ensures that the model does not become biased towards specific pixel intensities.
4. **Data Augmentation:** Since anomalies are rare, augmentation techniques such as **horizontal flipping, rotation, brightness variation, and Gaussian noise addition** are applied to normal frames to improve generalization and prevent overfitting.

For motion-aware learning, **Optical Flow vectors** are computed between consecutive frames to capture movement patterns. This ensures that the model can effectively differentiate normal movements from unusual activities, even when the changes are subtle.

C. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is performed using a combination of **Convolutional Autoencoders (CAE) for spatial features** [17] and **Optical Flow for motion features**[18]. This hybrid approach allows the model to learn both **appearance-based and motion-based anomalies**.

EarlyThe Convolutional Autoencoder extracts high-level spatial representations from input frames. The encoder consists of stacked convolutional layers with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation, which gradually reduce the dimensionality while capturing essential structural information. The decoder reconstructs the input frames using transposed convolution layers, ensuring that normal frames are

reconstructed accurately, while anomalies result in reconstruction errors.

Since anomalies are often characterized by sudden or unexpected movements, the model uses Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (ConvLSTM) layers to learn motion patterns across multiple frames[19]. Unlike traditional LSTMs, ConvLSTMs use convolution operations within their recurrent cells, making them ideal for modeling spatial-temporal dependencies in video sequences.

To improve the model's sensitivity to motion anomalies, Optical Flow is used to compute pixel-wise displacement vectors between consecutive frames. This helps capture motion inconsistencies that may not be evident in static frame analysis. The Optical Flow features are integrated into the model alongside the reconstructed frames, providing additional cues for detecting anomalies based on movement deviations.

Instead of using Mean Squared Error as a reconstruction loss, this model employs Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) loss to measure how similar the reconstructed frames are to the input frames[20]. SSIM focuses on preserving perceptual and structural details, making it highly effective in distinguishing normal from anomalous events.

D. Training

TABLE2: DETAILS OF THE SYSTEM USED

Hardware Platform		Software Platform	
CPU	Intel Xeon(R) Gold 6242R @3.10 GHz x 80	OS	Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS
GPU	NVIDIA RTX A5000	Framework	YOLO and Roboflow 3.0
RAM	256 GB	Programming	Python 3.10.x

The training phase focuses on learning the distribution of normal activity patterns using **only normal frames from the dataset**. The Convolutional Autoencoder and ConvLSTM network are trained jointly, while Optical Flow features are recomputed for integration into the final detection pipeline.

Procedure :

1. **Batch Formation:** Training frames are grouped into **fixed-length sequences** of 50 frames to capture temporal dependencies.
2. **Loss Function:** The model is optimized using a combination of **SSIM loss for spatial reconstruction** and **Mean Absolute Error for motion differences**.
3. **Optimizer:** The Adam optimizer with a **learning rate of 0.0001** is used for stable and efficient convergence.

4. **Regularization:** Dropout and batch normalization are applied to prevent overfitting and ensure stable gradient flow.
5. **Early Stopping:** The training process is monitored using a validation set, and early stopping is applied to prevent unnecessary overfitting.

After training, the model is capable of accurately reconstructing normal frames while producing high reconstruction errors for anomalous frames.

E. Testing

The trained model is evaluated on the test dataset, which includes both normal and abnormal activities. The model computes reconstruction errors for each test frame, and an anomaly score is assigned based on a weighted combination of SSIM loss and Optical Flow differences. By analysing both spatial and temporal inconsistencies, the model determines whether a given frame contains anomalous behaviour. The effectiveness of the model is assessed using various evaluation metrics to ensure robustness in real-world scenarios.

For each test frame, the model measures the difference between the original input frame and the reconstructed output using SSIM loss. Since the model has been trained to accurately reconstruct only normal frames, a high SSIM loss indicates a significant deviation from learned patterns, suggesting the presence of an anomaly. The reconstruction errors are computed for each frame, and a threshold is applied to classify the frames as normal or anomalous.

Motion-based anomaly detection is incorporated using Optical Flow[21], which captures pixel-wise motion differences between consecutive frames. Since abnormal activities often involve sudden or irregular motion patterns, the model analyses Optical Flow features to detect inconsistencies in movement. If the motion deviates significantly from normal activity patterns, the corresponding frame is flagged as anomalous. This additional motion-aware feature extraction enhances the model's ability to detect anomalies that might not be evident from static frame analysis alone.

To improve the reliability of anomaly detection, a dynamic thresholding approach is applied instead of using a fixed threshold. The model utilizes Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis to determine the optimal threshold dynamically[22]. By evaluating the trade-off between the True Positive Rate and False Positive Rate, the model selects a threshold that maximizes anomaly detection performance while minimizing false alarms. This ensures that the model adapts to variations in test data, improving generalization across different surveillance scenarios.

The final evaluation of the model is conducted using multiple performance metrics. Precision and recall are measured to assess the accuracy of anomaly classification, where precision indicates the proportion of correctly detected anomalies out of all detected anomalies, and recall represents the proportion of actual anomalies that were correctly identified. The F1-score is used as a balanced metric that considers both precision

and recall, providing a more comprehensive assessment of model performance. Additionally, the AUC-ROC curve is analysed to evaluate the model's ability to distinguish between normal and anomalous frames[23]. A higher AUC value indicates better discrimination capability, making it a valuable indicator of overall model effectiveness.

Through the testing phase, the model's ability to generalize to unseen scenarios is validated. The integration of SSIM-based reconstruction loss with Optical Flow enables the model to accurately detect both spatial and motion-based anomalies. By leveraging dynamic thresholding and rigorous performance evaluation, the model ensures reliable abnormal activity detection in real-world surveillance environments.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Result

The trained model was evaluated on the test dataset, which included both normal and abnormal activities. The model computed reconstruction errors for each test frame, assigning an anomaly score based on a weighted combination of SSIM loss and Optical Flow differences. By analysing both spatial and temporal inconsistencies, the model determined whether a given frame contained anomalous behaviour. The effectiveness of the model was assessed using various evaluation metrics to ensure robustness in real-world scenarios.

Reconstruction error analysis [24] showed that normal frames exhibited low reconstruction errors, indicating that the model effectively learned normal activity patterns. In contrast, anomalous frames resulted in higher reconstruction errors, confirming the model's sensitivity to deviations from learned patterns. The frame-wise reconstruction errors were used to assign anomaly scores, where a high anomaly score indicated the likelihood of an abnormal event. To refine detection accuracy, the 96th percentile of the reconstruction error distribution was selected as the anomaly threshold, ensuring that only the most significant deviations were classified as anomalies. This dynamic thresholding approach helped mitigate false positives and improved overall model reliability.

Fig. 5 : Frame-wise Anomaly Scores

Fig. 6 : Frame-wise Reconstruction Error Graph

Fig.7 : Histogram of Reconstruction Errors

To further interpret the model’s performance, anomaly visualization techniques[25] were applied. The original frame, reconstructed frame, error heatmap, and ground truth anomaly masks were compared to assess the effectiveness of the anomaly detection framework. The heatmaps revealed that the model successfully highlighted anomalous regions, particularly in scenarios where sudden movements or unusual activities occurred, such as running, fighting, or loitering. However, certain false positives were observed, primarily in scenarios where complex background textures or lighting variations caused the model to generate higher-than-expected reconstruction errors. This suggests that while the autoencoder-based approach is effective in identifying major anomalies, additional refinement using motion-aware techniques, such as Optical Flow or Temporal Attention Mechanisms, could further improve anomaly localization.

The model’s effectiveness was quantitatively evaluated using standard performance metrics, including precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC. The results obtained were as follows: Precision of 0.626, Recall of 0.065, F1-score of 0.105, and an AUC score of 0.570. The low recall value indicated that the model struggled to detect all anomalies, likely due to certain subtle anomalies not causing sufficiently high reconstruction errors. This is a common limitation in autoencoder-based anomaly detection, as the model may

sometimes reconstruct certain anomalies too well, reducing their anomaly scores. The moderate precision value suggested that when the model classified a frame as anomalous, it was relatively accurate in doing so. However, the low F1-score indicated a significant trade-off between precision and recall. The AUC-ROC score of 0.570 suggested

that the model had some capability in distinguishing between normal and anomalous frames, but there was room for improvement. The use of Optical Flow and SSIM loss improved performance compared to traditional Mean Squared Error-based autoencoder models, but further enhancement was needed to improve recall without excessively increasing false positives.

Fig.8 : Visualisation of original and reconstructed frame for a normal scene-1

Fig 9 : Visualisation of original and reconstructed frame for a normal scene-2

Fig 10 : Visualisation of original and reconstructed frame for a normal scene-3

B. Discussion

The proposed model demonstrated strong potential for unsupervised abnormal activity detection, particularly in

identifying sudden and motion-based anomalies. The integration of SSIM loss helped in detecting structural anomalies, while the use of ConvLSTM improved temporal modeling. The model's ability to learn normal activity patterns without requiring labeled anomalies made it highly scalable for real-world deployment. However, several limitations were observed. The low recall value suggested that certain subtle anomalies were not detected effectively. This could be due to the model's ability to partially reconstruct some abnormal frames, reducing their anomaly scores. Additionally, lighting variations, background clutter, and occlusions in the test dataset introduced false positives, affecting precision. The performance of the model could be further improved by incorporating attention-based mechanisms, adaptive thresholding techniques, and multi-scale feature extraction to enhance anomaly discrimination.

To address the observed limitations and enhance anomaly detection performance, several improvements can be considered. Enhancing motion awareness by integrating more advanced motion modeling techniques, such as Flow-Guided Feature Learning[26] or Spatiotemporal Transformers[27], could improve the model's ability to detect motion-based anomalies. Instead of using a fixed percentile for thresholding, an adaptive anomaly detection framework that dynamically adjusts based on scene context could improve recall. Incorporating multi-scale convolutional networks could help capture both local and global anomalies, improving precision and recall. Combining Autoencoders with Generative Adversarial Networks[28] or Contrastive Learning could improve anomaly representation learning, leading to better generalization. Additionally, optimizing the model for real-time inference using pruned architectures and edge-based AI acceleration could enable practical implementation in surveillance applications.

The results indicated that the proposed unsupervised anomaly detection framework was capable of identifying abnormal activities in surveillance footage with moderate precision but required further refinement to improve recall. While the model successfully distinguished between normal and anomalous frames, subtle anomalies and high reconstruction accuracy for certain abnormal frames limited overall recall performance. Future research will focus on incorporating more advanced motion-aware techniques, optimizing the model for real-time deployment, and improving adaptive thresholding strategies to enhance detection robustness.

IV. CONCLUSION

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) This research presents an unsupervised deep learning framework for abnormal activity detection in surveillance videos, leveraging a combination of Convolutional Autoencoders, Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory networks, and Optical Flow-based motion analysis. The model is designed to learn normal activity patterns from video sequences and detect anomalies based on reconstruction errors and motion inconsistencies. Unlike

traditional supervised approaches, which require large labelled datasets with both normal and anomalous instances, the proposed method operates in an unsupervised setting, making it more scalable and adaptable to real-world surveillance applications.

The evaluation of the model on the ShanghaiTech Campus dataset demonstrated its effectiveness in detecting anomalous activities based on both spatial and temporal inconsistencies. The results showed that the model could successfully reconstruct normal frames with low error while generating higher reconstruction errors for anomalous frames. The integration of Structural Similarity Index loss improved perceptual fidelity in anomaly detection, ensuring that fine-grained anomalies were better captured compared to traditional Mean Squared Error-based approaches. Additionally, Optical Flow analysis provided a motion-sensitive feature extraction mechanism, allowing the model to differentiate between normal and abnormal motion patterns effectively.

Despite its strengths, the model exhibited certain limitations, particularly in recall performance. Some subtle anomalies were not detected effectively due to the model's ability to partially reconstruct abnormal frames, reducing their anomaly scores. This issue highlights the challenge of autoencoder-based anomaly detection, where the model may generalize too well and inadvertently reconstruct anomalous frames with low errors. Additionally, variations in lighting conditions, complex background textures, and occlusions led to some false positives, affecting precision. The Receiver Operating Characteristic-based thresholding method improved the balance between precision and recall, but further improvements are necessary to enhance detection robustness.

Future work will focus on several key areas to improve the overall performance of the model. First, incorporating more advanced motion modeling techniques, such as Spatiotemporal Transformers or Flow-Guided Feature Learning, could enhance the model's ability to capture motion anomalies more effectively. Second, an adaptive thresholding mechanism that dynamically adjusts based on scene context could improve recall while minimizing false positives. Third, exploring multi-scale convolutional architectures could help capture both local and global anomalies, leading to a more comprehensive feature extraction process. Additionally, integrating hybrid approaches, such as combining autoencoders with Generative Adversarial Networks or Contrastive Learning, could further improve the model's ability to learn distinctive anomaly representations. Finally, optimizing the model for real-time deployment through lightweight architectures and edge-based AI acceleration will be essential for practical applications in live surveillance scenarios.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the feasibility of using an unsupervised deep learning approach for anomaly detection in surveillance videos. The proposed model successfully integrates spatial and temporal feature learning, enhancing anomaly detection accuracy through a combination of Structural Similarity Index loss and Optical Flow-based motion analysis. While the results are promising,

further research is needed to overcome existing limitations and improve the model's generalizability across diverse real-world scenarios. With continuous advancements in deep learning and computer vision, the development of highly accurate and scalable anomaly detection systems will play a crucial role in enhancing public safety, automated surveillance, and intelligent monitoring applications.

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